

Conference Abstract

Identification and invasive potential of Asian weatherfish in Europe

Thomas Klefoth[‡], Isabel Tanzberger[‡], Meret Neske[‡], Asia Gabajdulina[‡]

[‡] Hochschule Bremen, Bremen, Germany

Corresponding author: Thomas Klefoth (thomas.klefoth@hs-bremen.de)

Received: 07 Dec 2025 | Published: 30 Dec 2025

Citation: Klefoth T, Tanzberger I, Neske M, Gabajdulina A (2025) Identification and invasive potential of Asian weatherfish in Europe. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e181677. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e181677>

Abstract

Asian weatherfish are increasingly spreading in Germany and Europe. However, the exact species composition of the non-native fishes and their invasion potential have been insufficiently studied. We integrated genetic, morphological, and behavioural methods to identify and assess the invasive potential of Asian weatherfish (*Misgurnus* spp.) and their threat to the endangered native *Misgurnus fossilis* in northern Germany. COI sequencing of 107 specimens confirmed the presence of *Misgurnus anguillicaudatus* and indicated possible occurrence of additional cryptic species, though species-level resolution remained limited due to genetic overlap. Morphological investigations, together with an extensive review of peer-reviewed and grey Asian literature on morphological characteristics, revealed insufficient morphological differentiation within Asian weatherfish. This was either because no species other than *Misgurnus anguillicaudatus* were present in our samples or because the morphological characteristics were also overlapping. Additionally, two-way choice behavioural experiments were conducted to compare habitat preferences of European and Asian weatherfish, testing muddy sediment against sand and gravel. Under controlled conditions, Asian weatherfish showed greater swimming activity, oxygen-independent air-breathing, and higher burrowing intensity than European weatherfish. The Asian species tolerated all sediment types, whereas *Misgurnus fossilis* preferred mud and avoided gravel. Our results demonstrate that non-native Asian weatherfish possess enhanced morphological and ecological plasticity, as well as greater dispersal capacity, which likely facilitates the competitive displacement of native species. This underscores the need for robust

molecular and morphological identification methods and targeted conservation measures to secure European weatherfish populations against the advancing spread of invasive congeners.

Keywords

loach, invasive species, conservation, genetics, behaviour

Presenting author

Thomas Klefoth

Ethics and security

The research was completed following German legislation for animal experimentation, approved by "Die Senatorin für Gesundheit, Frauen und Verbraucherschutz" under grant no. TV 181.

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.